

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES

PAPER ID: IJPS/230112178

ISSN: 0975-4725

Certificate of Publication

This is to certify that

Pratiksha Udawant, Corresponding Author

Published a paper entitled

**"Review Of Monkeypox Virus :Symptoms ,Pathogenesis ,Diagnosis
And Treatment"**

Volume 2 – Issue 1 - 2024

ijpsjournal.com

Editor-In-Chief

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES

PAPER ID: IJPS/230112178

ISSN: 0975-4725

Certificate of Publication

This is to certify that

Sabafarin Shaikh, Co-Author

Published a paper entitled

**"Review Of Monkeypox Virus :Symptoms ,Pathogenesis ,Diagnosis
And Treatment"**

Volume 2 – Issue 1 - 2024

ijpsjournal.com

Editor-In-Chief

PAPER ID: IJPS/230112178

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES

ISSN: 0975-4725

Certificate of Publication

This is to certify that

Khare Komal, Co-Author

Published a paper entitled

**"Review Of Monkeypox Virus :Symptoms ,Pathogenesis ,Diagnosis
And Treatment"**

Volume 2 – Issue 1 - 2024

ijpsjournal.com

Editor-In-Chief

PAPER ID: IJPS/230112178

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES

ISSN: 0975-4725

Certificate of Publication

This is to certify that

Mayur S. Bhosle, Co-Author

Published a paper entitled

**"Review Of Monkeypox Virus :Symptoms ,Pathogenesis ,Diagnosis
And Treatment"**

Volume 2 – Issue 1 - 2024

ijpsjournal.com

Editor-In-Chief

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES

PAPER ID: IJPS/230112178

ISSN: 0975-4725

Certificate of Publication

This is to certify that

Sushmita Chavan, Co-Author

Published a paper entitled

**"Review Of Monkeypox Virus :Symptoms ,Pathogenesis ,Diagnosis
And Treatment"**

Volume 2 – Issue 1 - 2024

ijpsjournal.com

Editor-In-Chief

